

THE IMPORTANCE OF PLOT-BASED ROLE-PLAYING GAMES IN THE COMPREHENSIVE DEVELOPMENT OF PRESCHOOL CHILDREN.

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Abstract

This article analyzes the role of role-playing games in the development stages of preschool-aged children. During play, children focus not only on the material world of adults but also on adopting social relationships and roles. Play activities develop with age; younger preschoolers tend to prefer individual play, while middle and older preschoolers learn to follow game rules and establish social interactions. The article also discusses symbolic forms of play, drawing, and construction games as key factors that influence children's thinking and creative abilities.

Keywords: preschool-aged children, middle or older preschool age, play, object play, role-playing games, rule-based games, school.

In New Uzbekistan, special attention is given to the preschool education system, and legal and regulatory frameworks have been established for the development of children aged 3 to 7. These frameworks aim to ensure access to preschool education and create the necessary legal and normative conditions for children's comprehensive intellectual, moral, aesthetic, and physical development [1].

Each preschool-aged child has unique cognitive activities, willpower, character, and behavioral traits. In the educational process of preschool institutions, it is essential to recognize these characteristics and adopt an individualized approach based on them. Only by considering these features can every educator successfully fulfill their primary task—providing quality education and upbringing to the younger generation. Therefore, a deep understanding of the foundations of developmental and pedagogical psychology, which are special fields of psychology, is considered crucial for every educator.

Psychology consists of several branches, among which developmental psychology holds particular significance. Developmental psychology studies the psychological growth of individuals, as well as the characteristics of personal

development during childhood, adolescence, youth, adulthood, and old age. Despite numerous fundamental studies conducted in this field, a comprehensive description of human psychological development across all life stages has yet to be achieved [5].

Throughout childhood, the primary activities of children develop progressively, including object manipulation games, constructive individual object play, group role-playing games, individual and collective creative activities, competitive games, interactive games, and household chores. Younger preschool children mainly engage in play with objects and various toys on their own. Through object-based and constructive play, they develop perception, memory, imagination, thinking processes, and motor skills.

Since young children (sometimes even in small groups) have limited life experience and activities, their games primarily reflect specific people and their actions. For example, they may imitate their mother, father, older siblings, or preschool teacher.

In the play activities of middle and older preschool-aged children, character portrayals begin to take on a more generalized nature. Gradually, as children reach the middle preschool period, their games become more collective, involving an increasing number of participants. Observing children's individual characteristics during group games becomes easier, as these games reflect not only adults' interactions with objects but also their interpersonal relationships, which children tend to imitate.

Moreover, in group games, children portray complex aspects of human life and activities. For example, in the "train" game, various roles are assigned, such as the train driver, coal stoker, conductors, ticket inspectors, station staff, and passengers. These collective games resemble the activities of actors because each child strives to perform their role well while also ensuring they do not deviate from the overall storyline of the game. This dynamic requires children to engage all their abilities.

Role-based group games also demand that children follow strict rules and complete specific tasks within the given framework. Therefore, such games hold significant psychological value. They foster qualities like willpower, politeness, adherence to rules, discipline, and other positive character traits [3].

The most important aspect of these games is that children do not merely imitate adults' interactions with objects; rather, they focus on human relationships and, more specifically, on role imitation. Children identify the roles and rules that structure

these interactions and strictly monitor their adherence within the game, making an effort to follow them as well.

Thematic role-playing games vary, reflecting children's familiarity with real-life experiences. The roles that children reenact in their games can be family-related, educational, fairy tale characters, or professional roles. These roles can be played by adults, other children, or even by substitute objects such as toys and dolls.

This stage of development is closely linked to the emergence of two essential activities necessary for growth: work and learning. The sequence of how children adapt to play, work, and learning can be determined, leading to the conditional division of preschool age into three periods for analytical purposes:

Early preschool age (3–4 years)

Middle preschool age (4–5 years)

Late preschool age (5–6 years)

This classification is used in developmental psychology to track rapid and qualitative changes in children's psychology and behavior. Young preschoolers typically play alone, in accordance with their stage of development. Through their object-based and constructive play, they refine their perception, memory, imagination, thinking, and motor skills.

At this age, children typically reenact the actions of adults they observe in their daily lives through role-playing games. During middle and late preschool years, role-playing games develop further; however, they significantly differ from those in early preschool age in terms of introduced themes, roles, and game rules.

Many real-life objects are replaced with symbolic substitutes, marking the beginning of symbolic play. For example, a simple building block can represent furniture, vehicles, people, or animals, regardless of its original purpose in the game. In these games, following rules and maintaining social interactions, such as hierarchy and subordination, become central elements.[2,4]

For the first time, leadership emerges, and children begin developing organizational skills and competencies.

Along with role-playing games, another symbolic form of individual play activity is drawing. Gradually, imagination, creativity, and thinking become more involved in this process. Over time, the child moves from simply depicting what they see to drawing what they know, remember, or invent.

Competitive games are classified separately, as the desire to win and achieve success strongly attracts children. It is believed that these games help shape and reinforce the motivation for success.

During the late preschool years, constructive play begins to transition into a form of labor activity. In the process of play, children start creating, building, and making things that are useful in everyday life. Through such games, they acquire basic labor skills and practical abilities, and their problem-solving thinking develops actively.

Children also learn how to use various household tools and objects. Their ability to plan their actions emerges and improves, while their motor skills, cognitive operations, imagination, and creativity are refined.

At this age, children particularly enjoy engaging in creative activities, especially drawing. By analyzing what and how a child expresses in their drawings, one can understand how they perceive the surrounding world, as well as their memory, imagination, and thought processes. Through their drawings, children attempt to convey their impressions and knowledge of the external world.

The article analyzes role-playing games among preschool children and their psychological significance. Through play, children internalize social roles, develop rules, and learn to follow them. While younger children tend to prefer individual play, older preschoolers focus more on symbolic games, roles, and rules.

During play, leadership and organizational skills emerge and strengthen. Drawing plays a crucial role in the development of a child's thinking, enhancing their imagination and creative thinking.

In the later preschool years, constructive play begins to resemble labor activities, fostering practical thinking and planning skills. In this way, children prepare for social life through play while developing their creative and intellectual potential.

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